

WAVELET TRANSFORM BASED UNDERWATER IMAGE RESTORATION USING WEIGHT MAP TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

A fusion-based image restoration system has been proposed in this research to enhance underwater images that suffer from non-uniform lighting, low contrast, blurriness, and vilified color. The proposed technique is based on the fusion-based principle, which focuses on input images, weight map, and white balance measurement from a degraded underwater image. Luminance, Chromatic, and Saliency weight maps are applied to build an image that corrects the flaws in the original image or a noisy image with poor visibility. This research offers a new image fusion strategy-based single picture enhancement approach. The method works by first applying white balance and global contrast enhancement technologies to the original image, then using two adapted versions of the original image as inputs, which are then weighted by maps. The improved results are obtained by computing the weight total of the two inputs per-pixel. 2D Wavelet Transform as fusion operator and Gaussian and Laplacian Pyramid algorithms used in this study. The output demonstrates that the proposed enhancement algorithm can obtain a well visual result.

Key Terms:Image Enhancement, Underwater Image Restoration, Wavelet Transform, Weight Maps

1. INTRODUCTION

Underwater imaging is difficult due to the illumination properties existing in different environments. The underwater images degrade more than

a normal image which have poor visibility due to the improper illumination and obstruction of the propagated light. Due to various scattering and absorption, light generally reduces exponentially with distance and depth. The light direction is influenced, causing the image to blur. This light reduction creates a blurred appearance, while the scattered light return affects the contrast. The objects in the sea water which are more than ten meters are almost hazy with faded color as their wavelengths are affected. All these factors result in an image with poor contrast which appear blurred and hazy. There are several methods and strategies to restore the degraded image. To reach the image with maximum perfection, certain operations to be performed. Here using some common methods in the initial stage and followed by an enhancement process. Finally, get the results with more attractive than the earlier one.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A fusion-based approach is proposed in this study, which generates two different copies of the input images. Luminance, Chromatic and saliency are then used to calculate weights. Two input images are combined with the stated weights using a multi-scale fusion technique to provide an augmented image with better global contrast and detail information. In addition, the fusion process uses three weight maps to indicate brightness, global contrast, Chromatic, and original saliency.

The fusion-based strategy has a high degree of flexibility because it can be integrated with other strategies to obtain more precise inputs and adjust the weights. The choice of inputs and weights is the fundamental variation between fusion algorithms that makes them application specific.

2.1 Weight Maps

A derived input alone cannot restore the de hazed image and this imposes the requirement of the map of the assigned weights. White balance and enhancing the contrast are preliminary process to the image in RGB space. To describe the saturation and contrast of images better while observe color objects, luminance weight map, chromatic weight map and saliency weight map to measure and extract more details of the input image are used. Then integrated into one image, we can get more accurate results. The following are the instruction of three weight maps.

a) Luminance Weight Map: Luminance weight map manages the luminance gain in the output image. This map computes the standard deviation between every R, G and B color channel and each pixel luminance L of the input. The two input images are converted from RGB

space to HSV space, for the component of V is the component of luminance. This weight map plays a role of balancing the brightness.

b) Chromatic Weight Map: Chromatic weight map controls the saturation gain in the output image. Chroma is the purity of the color, it is used to describe the saturation of the image, the higher saturation is, the more vivid the color is. To obtain this map, for every pixel is computed the distance between its saturation value S and the maximum of the saturation range using a Gauss curve:

$$d = \exp\left(-\frac{(S - S_{max})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

The standard deviation $\sigma = 0.3$. Thus, weights close to zero are assigned to the pixels with smaller saturation while the most saturated pixels have weights close to one.

c) Saliency Weight Map: The main information of the image is concentrated in only a small number of critical areas and it usually focused on the sudden change in the image or the contour of the image with the biggest curvature, and these will be reflecting by the saliency map. This map reflects the contrast between a particular region and its adjacent areas. If the area's contrast become more obvious, it will be easier to attract the attention, and it will have greater significance. Saliency map can make the edge of the original image to be highlighted. After extracting the contours of the image, the process increases its corresponding weight value, to achieve the result of image contrast enhanced.

2.2 Image Fusion:

The main objective of image fusion is to combine the multiple images from the different path with better resolution. These images provide a precise description, and which is more adaptable for the human visual system. While fusing, it doesn't add any extra

features and at the same time reduce the unfortunate characteristics of source images. Different images from different source exhibit different spatial and spectral characteristics. Here using image fusion algorithm based 2D-DWT.

2.3 2D Discrete Wavelet Transform:

The working of the discrete wavelet transform starts with decomposition. The input signal is decomposed into a set of functions known as wavelets. Initially, four blocks of the frequency band which are Low Low (LL), Low High (LH), High Low (HL) and High High (HH) frequency bands. Each band is again divided into four and followed by the further proceeding. Here discrete Wavelet Transform uses two function sets such as scaling, and wavelet related to low and high pass filters. It indicates that a few samples in a system can represent the whole signal.

Fig. 2. Model of DWT

2.4 Gaussian and Laplacian Pyramids:

In the fusion process, the inputs are weighted by specific computed maps to conserve the most significant detected features. The Proposed approach is simply blending the inputs weighted by several maps. The strategy combines the input information in a per-pixel fashion minimizing the loss of the image structure after the two input Image, the three weight maps for each input image:

wL_1, wL_2 (luminance weight map)

wC_1, wC_2 (chromatic weight map)

wS_1, wS_2 (saliency weight map)

To facilitate the subsequent weighted fusion. Each weight map must be normalized first and the normalized value of the illuminance map of the input 1:

$$NwL_1 = wL_1 / (wL_1 + wL_2)$$

$$NwL_2 = wL_2 / (wL_1 + wL_2)$$

By analogy, the normalized value of other maps of 1 L is NwC_1, NwS_1. The same method to get the values for 2 L. The following step is the linear integration of the three weighted value. W to express the final weight which is calculated as below:

$$W_i = a * NwL_i + b * NwC_i + c * NwS_i$$

In the formula a,b,c are the three weighted value of the coefficient. The value of a,b,c are all set to 1. The output image can be described as:

$$F^{(i,j)} = \sum_k m_k * W_k^{(i,j)} I_k^{(i,j)}$$

In the formula, m_k are the coefficient of the two input images 1 I and 2 I ,each pixel (i, j) of the output F is computed by adding the inputs I_k weighted by corresponding normalized weight maps W_k .In this paper, each input is decomposed into a pyramid by applying Laplacian operator at different scales. Similarly, for each normalized weight map W a Gaussian pyramid is computed. Considering that both the Gaussian and Laplacian pyramids have the same number of levels, the mixing between the Laplacian inputs and Gaussian normalized weights is performed at each level independently yielding the fused pyramid:

$$F_l^{(i,j)} = \sum_k G_l \{ \overline{W}_k^{(i,j)} \} L_l \{ I_k^{(i,j)} \}$$

where l represents the number of the pyramid levels and L {I} is the Laplacian version of the input I while G{W} represents the Gaussian version of the normalized weight map of the W. This step is performed successively for each pyramid layer, in a bottom-up manner. The final

output image J is obtained by adding the fused contribution of all inputs. Through low-pass filtering and down-sample process, Gaussian pyramid can be generated. Finally, fusing the two weighted inputs to yield the fused pyramid F to get the final restored underwater image.

Fig 3. The two inputs and the three weight maps

Fig4. Fusion wavelet based restored image and histogram

3. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

To evaluate on the results of the images, MSE and PSNR of the image are taken account to quantify the resultant images for comparison. Comparison in the term of MSE and PSNR with previous method – i.e. when compared with other weight map techniques and fusion

technology. The below table show the comparative value of mean square ratio and peak signal noise ratio for the resultant image of fusion based restoration system. The fusion based method has the lowest MSE compared to the others and PSNR values are the highest.

3.1 Mean Square Error (MSE):

(MSE) and (PSNR) are used to compare image compression quality. The MSE represents the cumulative squared error between the compressed and the original image, whereas PSNR represents a measure of the peak error. The lower the value of MSE, the lower the error.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{M \times N} \sum_{M,N} [I_1(m,n) - I_2(m,n)]^2$$

3.2 Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR):

The PSNR block computes the peak signal-to-noise ratio, in decibels, between two images. ... The higher the PSNR, the better the quality of the compressed, or reconstructed image.

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{2^B - 1}{\sqrt{MSE}} \right)^2$$

3.3 Mean Square Error and Peak Signal to Noise ratio

Results:

Input image	Output image	Method	MSE	PSNR
	Previous Method	6.85	39.81	
		Proposed Method	0.09	58.49
	Previous Method	5.85	38.20	
		Proposed Method	0.91	48.59
	Previous Method	6.23	37.52	
		Proposed Method	0.44	51.70

4. CONCLUSION

The proposed method of using weight map techniques and the 2d-DWT model resulted in the images having the lowest MSE and maximum PSNR values when compared in this research. To give the highest accuracy and clarity for the restored image, the proposed system processes the weight map first, followed by wavelet transformations.

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